

Remittance and Nepal: Unveiling the Impact on Economy and Society

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Abstract

According to the IMF, remittance is the term used to describe when migrants send home a portion of their earnings in the form of cash or commodities to support their families. The newest wave of globalization has made remittances and migration popular buzzwords. *According to UNHCR*, over 3.6% of people on Earth reside outside of their country of birth. That translates to 281 million people who reside outside of their country of origin. To put it simply, remittance refers to the act of those 281 million people sending a portion of their dependents to the home country.

In the context of Nepal, remittance inflow has attracted intense attention in the Nepali macroeconomic environment as the trend of emigration of Nepali workers has risen over the past decade. In the first seven months of the current fiscal year, 2022–23, the nation received remittances totaling more than Rs 689 billion. Details of the first seven months of the current fiscal year have been given by the central bank, and they show a 27.1 percent increase over the prior fiscal year. Nepal is seen as a remittance-based economy as reported in 2020, the percentage of remittance contribution to GDP is around 23.4 percent. Remittance in Nepal has also been working as a catalyst in poverty reduction. *According to NLSS*, 56 percent of Nepalese households receive remittance and one in every two rural households receive remittance.

Labor remittance can be characterized as a complex phenomenon that encompasses a range of microeconomic ideas. The discernible effects of remittance on the correction of balance of payments, improvement of living standards, eradication of poverty, and enhancement of education are readily apparent.

History of Migration in Nepal

In Nepal, the history of foreign migration dates to 1816 AD, when the British recruited members of the Nepali Gorkha Army because of their renown for valor. Even in modern times, this pattern is still observed, and young population in hilly areas are encouraged to join the Gurkhas by it. Sardar Bhim Bahadur Pandey explains in his book (*Tyas Bakhat ko Nepal, Part 1 pp 17*) from 1971 to 1975, about 200,000 young men of the Gorkhali platoon, who went to fight the Great War in Europe, returned to Nepal on leave in 1977 after the war. Not only did they bring INR 1,300 lakhs, but they also brought foreigners or customs, food, and drinks.

Following the restoration of multi-party democracy and liberalization in 1990, international migration increased even further. The internal strife caused by the Maoist insurgency, which started in 1996, as well as a downturn in Nepal's carpet industry encouraged more people to migrate to other countries as the nation was opening to the rest of the globe. Many people were displaced during the ten-year civil war between the Government and the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist), both within and to foreign countries.

According to Nepal Rastra Bank, a total of 137,475 Nepalese workers, including both institutional and individual employees, have obtained initial approval for foreign employment. Similarly, 68,841 Nepalese workers have obtained renewal entry approval. These figures were 196,735 and 87,428 respectively, in the preceding year, with the bulk of them going to Malaysia: 219,359 annually. Furthermore, 277,272 individuals extended their visas to work abroad. If we look more closely, the majority of those who extended their visas from 2020 till now were migrants in Qatar. We might infer that most of these individuals labored under difficult circumstances to build the stadiums in Qatar for the FIFA World Cup in 2022. Around 400,000 Nepalese laborers are engaged in Qatar across a variety of industries and have made significant contributions to the construction of the extensive infrastructural projects necessary to host the 2022 FIFA World Cup.

History of Nepalis in American soil leads back to 1939, the first official visit by a Nepalese official to the United States was conducted by General Krishna Rana, Nepal's Minister in London. General Shinga Rana, his successor, paid a visit in 1945 after that. Commanding General Baber Rana accompanied a Nepalese mission to the United States in the summer of 1946, where they were entertained by the State and War Departments for several weeks. Ever since going to the USA has been a popular destination of Nepalese people. In the recent report of *American Community Survey*, there are approximately 208,000 Nepalese in the USA in 2020. This number has increased significantly since 2010, when there were around 59,000 Nepalese at that time.

Additionally, it is important to highlight that migration is not always for foreign employment migration. *UNESCO* figures show that the number of students from Nepal travelling abroad to study has more than doubled from 44,255 in 2017 to 95,268 in 2022. Of the 95,268 Nepalese students who left the country to study abroad in 2022, 40,752 (42.77%) went to Australia, 18,436 (19.35%) went to Japan, 13,574 (14.24%) went to India, and 12,660 (13.28%) went to the United States.

Diversity Visa influencing migration.

Diversity Visa, one of the popular words among the Nepalese youth currently. The United States conducts the Diversity Immigrant Visa Lottery, often known as the DV Lottery, which chooses immigrants at random from all over the world to earn a green card and be allowed to join the nation. Additionally, the program offers people and families from Nepal the ability to move to the US. More than 600,000 Nepalese people apply each year, and 4,097 of them received the program's permanent resident status in the US in 2018. Additionally, 10,201 Nepalis were given permanent resident status last year, while 7,409 were awarded US citizenship.

Foreign Reserves

The term "Foreign Exchange Reserves" refers to the assets that a central bank keeps in reserve in convertible foreign currencies. Monetary policy is influenced by and supported by these reserves. In macroeconomics, foreign reserves are a hot issue since they affect the country's commerce. Since the exporters would not accept the home currency of the importing country, a nation must have foreign reserves to purchase products from international markets. Without sufficient reserves, a nation would not be able to pay for essential imports like crude oil, raw materials, medicine or

pay off its foreign debt. Insufficient reserves may also restrict a central bank's options for action in the case of a financial emergency.

It is seen that many Asian country lead the boards having the most foreign reserves. Brining Nepal into the discussion, Nepal has foreign exchange reserves amounting \$12.75 billion in mid- November 2023, compared with \$11.71 billion in mid-July, 2023. From the figure alongside, it can be seen that over the period Nepal has been improving the foreign reserves after the foreign reserves' crisis in early 2022. According to Nepal Rastra Bank, foreign currency reserves fell by more than 16 percent to 1.17tn Nepali rupees (\$9.59bn; £7.36bn) in the seven months to the middle of February. The improvement was mainly caused by strict regulation put by the government in the imports of “non-essentials” goods such as cars, cosmetics, gold, silver etc.

Remittance and its role in Foreign Reserves in Nepal

The major source of foreign reserve for any country can come in various ways: Remittance, export, international trade, tourism, foreign investments, and loans. Remittances provide a substantial source of foreign currency for Nepal. When Nepali workers send money back home, it adds to the foreign reserves held by the country.

Country	Reserves (USD Billions)
China	\$3,480
Japan	\$1,376
Switzerland	\$1,033
India	\$599
Nepal	\$10

Source: Investopedia (As of June 2022)

These reserves can be used to stabilize the exchange rate, finance imports, and cover external obligations. According to Nepal Rastra Bank, there are 21 foreign currency, convertible foreign currencies, that can be traded within the nation, or the central bank has and can be convertible with each other.

According to recent reports from Statista, the value of remittance sent to Nepal amounts to \$9.29 billion, where majority is from Malaysia. The foreign currency sent by migrant in form of remittance is exchanged in money exchanger and ultimately the foreign currency reaches the central bank. Thus, we can conclude the inflow of remittance causes the major change in the number of foreign reserves the nation holds. It is also required to keep in mind, the when the

remittance is sent, it increases the money supply of the home nation as the central bank keeps the foreign currency and distributes the equivalent extra home currency in the market.

This process is not just in Nepal, but it is applicable to all the nation. Remittance is the major source of foreign reserves to almost every country.

Remittance and its impact in Educations Sector

Remittance send can be used in many different sectors: real estate, education, commodities and many more. School enrollment and educational spending are the two primary ways that remittances have an impact on children and young people's education. Remittances can free up households' access to credit and enhance their spending on their children's and their own education (Cox Edwards and Ureta, 2003; Hanson and Woodruff, 2003; Yang, 2008). With no statistically significant impacts discovered for most nations, the study reveals very weak linkages between migration, remittances, and school attendance. However, there is a statistically significant correlation between remittances and youth school attendance rates in Burkina Faso and Côte d'Ivoire, particularly for males (Sophia Chae, Jennifer E. Glick: *Educational Selectivity of Migrants and Current School Enrollment in Four Sub-Saharan African Countries*)

In the case of Nepal, the exact data has been yet to be studied and researched, it can be assumed that over the years the as the more and more low earning people fly abroad, they tend to send money which is invested into their child education in the home country. Households receiving remittances may decide to invest more in their children’s education, for example by buying textbooks and other materials, tuition fees or moving children to better schools.

In the study done OECD, remittances are positively correlated with educational spending in five of the eight nations studied, which shows that migration and education are related in ways more than just school attendance. Remittance-receiving households are more likely to use the money for additional educational expenses. This conclusion is consistent with those of several other research (such as Chappell et al. (2010) and Medina and Cardona (2010).

There are concerns that more people are obtaining new work permits. As of July 1, of the current fiscal year, 2022/23, which ends on July 16, over 750,000 Nepali citizens have labor permits, up from approximately 650,000 the year before, according to the Department of Foreign Employment. The trend of going abroad for labor and sending money is just increasing and increasing.

<i>Year</i>	<i>Literacy %</i>	<i>Change %</i>
1991	32.98	
2001	48.61	15.63
2011	59.63	11.02
2018	67.91	8.28
2021	71.15	3.24

Source: Macrotrends

We can assume that as the receipts of remittance increased over the year, the literacy rate in Nepal also followed the similar trend.

Exchange Rates and Remittance

Bouhga-Hagbe, 2004, explained the exchange rate through the “substitution” and “wealth” effects could influence the level of remittance. When the Nepali currency depreciates, the goods produced inside the country becomes less expensive and the people abroad do not really need to send high volume of remittance to the home country. This enables migrants to substitute some goods in the home country for some more expensive goods in the country of residence. On the other hand, a devaluation or depreciation of the currency of the home nation allows its migrant residents to accumulate greater wealth, which encourages them to send back more money to buy even more products, such as constructing homes and investing in real estate, in the place of origin. This is the "wealth effect" of a depreciation or devaluation of the exchange rate. Additionally, migrants may borrow money or get advances to send back scheduled remittances in the future at a favorable exchange rate.

Adhikari (2018) utilized Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to analyze currency rates' effects on foreign exchange reserves throughout the period of 1975–2015 in Nepal, and the results showed that for every percentage point the rupee depreciated, foreign exchange reserves increased by 0.82 percentage points. Thus, it can be concluded that the exchange rate is the main factor affecting Nepal's foreign exchanger reserve.

III Effects of Remittance

Regarding the above subjects, the majority appears to be a positive indication. However, certain aspects of remittances have the potential to significantly deplete a nation's resources. the issue of inflation and real estate Bubble and Dutch illnesses among other pose a risk due to the substantial influx of remittances.

As previously mentioned in relation to the "*Tyas Bakhat ko Nepal*," Sardar Bhim Bahadur Pandey discusses that while the Nepali soldiers did bring in substantial foreign funds, the items they brought in were not restricted to currency and commodities. Additionally, they initiated a first wave of novelty among the general population regarding the external world. Certain practices and customs that have been detrimental to the nation.

The study "*The impact of remittance inflows on inflation: Evidence in Asian and the pacific developing countries*" found that remittance inflows significantly increase inflation in the countries studied. This is a very expected phenomenon as generally, we expect when there is an increase in the money supply in the nation, the general price level of the nation is increased, leading to inflation.

Similar effects can also be explained for the hike in real estate prices. Due to the lack of productive sector investments, several sources indicate that a significant portion of remittance inflows in Nepal is indeed invested in the real estate sector. The Nepal Rastra Bank's report on real estate financing in Nepal highlighted that the accelerating growth of remittances has led to a substantial amount of money being invested in the land and housing business.

Considering all the negative consequences associated with remittances, it is possible to deduce the presence of Dutch Diseases. This conclusion is reached by analyzing the growth of

remittances, real estate prices, and credit growth in financial institutions, while output and living standards continue to stall significantly.

Conclusion

Based on the areas studied above, it can be concluded that remittance has a significant impact across several sectors, influencing multiple factors within each area. One lesser-known consequence of remittance is the occurrence of Dutch diseases: described in literature, refers to the observable correlation between the growth of a certain sector in an economy and the subsequent decline of other sectors. This phenomenon has been extensively studied and documented in various scholarly works. In many countries that receive remittances, it is evident that when workers overseas transfer money from foreign nations, there is a discernible decrease in economic activity inside the home country. The farmer's wife, who provides for herself and her children, may cease agricultural activities upon receiving remittances. What impact does this have on the nation?

The decline in domestic activity has a direct impact on the volume of items manufactured, leading to a reduction in the gross domestic product. Furthermore, the utilization of remittances is limited solely to the importation of products, resulting in a significant deterioration of the nation's balance of payments. Moreover, upon the worker's return following their labor, they may be confronted with the prospect of unemployment.

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